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*Corresponding

Author: Rakesh Sharma
Department of
Biochemistry, SMMH
Government Medical
College, Saharanpur, Uttar
Pradesh

Repurposed Statins in Cancer: Innovations, Mechanisms, Combination Therapies and Nanotechnology

Rakesh Sharma

Department of Biochemistry, SMMH Government Medical
College, Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

Cholesterol-lowering statins act as repurposed drugs to enhance chemosensitivity, reduce chemotoxic, chemostatic, chemoresistance effects and radiation-toxicity. Statin drugs combined with concurrent chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy, initially target lipid metabolism to trigger pro-apoptosis, autophagy, antiproliferative, antiangiogenesis, immunosuppressant, anti-oxidant, cell cycle growth, control points, tumor microenvironment to reduce drug-resistance and delay the cancer progress to metastases in tumor cells. The clinical use of statin-chemoradiotherapy combinations in optimal doses is a new approach. Still dose-response and enhanced outcomes of statins are in infancy. It needs investigations on statin-statin, statin-chemo-radiotherapy, statin-immunosuppressor drug interactions, chemo-radiation dosage optimizations with patient safety. In available clinical trials, a subgroup analysis on prospective vs retrospective study design showed altered mechanisms of statin actions on cancer pathways and indicated the combined therapy benefits. The present study presents the concepts of statin-responsive cancer classification, a proposed criteria and prescription of statins combined with chemo-radiotherapy to target tumors, drug-drug interactions in cancer theranosis, cancer prediction and patient outcomes based on reported clinical trials. The optimized statins combined with chemotherapy with radiotherapy may reduce the toxicity and chemoresistance to enhance patient and clinical outcomes.

Keywords: Repurposed statins, Chemotherapy, Radiotherapy, Combined therapy, Policy and Criteria

INTRODUCTION

Cholesterol-lowering statin “re-purposed” combination therapies using nanotechnology are anticancer nanodrugs in cancer treatment and management. The concepts of cholesterol-lowering statins with possible anticancer potentials, pharmacological statins doses combined with chemotherapy, radiotherapy,

immunotherapy, cell cycle control, apoptosis, anticancer therapies against proliferation, inflammation, autophagy and metastasis, are exciting innovative areas.

Statins as monotherapy for cholesterol lowering, heart strengthening is in use since five decades by cardiologists as shown in Figure 1A.

Fig. 1A: (on top) Different statins in trimodal statin-chemo-radiotherapy design and statin effects on tumor progression and tumor microenvironment rich in immune cells and MSC[79]. (in middle) Arrows represent imaging of inhibitory effects [80] and [81]. At bottom, arrows show hypoxia-promoting apoptosis effects.

New innovations on hybrid ‘trimodal therapy’ statin in combination with chemodrugs and/or radiotherapy drugs are cancer treatment options available to oncologists because of synergistic effects, pleiotropic effects of “repurposed” statin

concurrent chemo-radiotherapy therapies and/or other alternate adjuvant therapies to treat the tumors, monitor tumor response and predict the tumor recurrence as shown in Figures 1B, 1C..

Fig. 1B: Role of statins to target different molecules and induce inhibition of tumor cell survival

Fig. 1C: Statins combined with chemoradiotherapy drugs perform induction-inhibition of different control points to reduce cytotoxicity and tumor resistance.

WHAT ARE STATINS?

The word “eais-ta-tin” refers to bi-cyclic ring compounds as inhibitor of the hydroxyl-methyl-glutamate Co-enzyme A reductase (HMG-CoA-R) enzyme needed for mevalonate formation and isoprenoid intermediates of cholesterol synthesis inside cells. There are three types of

statins: low-dose hydrophilic statins, high-dose hydrophobic statins, and high-dose repurposed statin-induced metabolic regulators, apoptosis-autophagy-immunostimulatory, cell cycle control point inhibitors and targeting proliferation statins as shown in in Figure 1A and Table 1.

Table 1: *Statin-loaded chemo-radiotherapy nanoformulations made of liposomes, micelle, emulsions, polymers used in clinical research.*

Nanomaterial /Nanoparticle	Statin + Chemodrug	Outcome
pH specific liposome	Simvastatin+Doxorubicin	Synergistic effect of SpHL-D-S, reduced cell migration Uterine leiomyoma-No significant change Colon cancer – Pronounced angiogenesis inhibition
Deformed liposome	Vorinostat+Simvastatin	Lewis Lung cancer – reduced angiogenesis, macrophages,T-cells
Hyaluronan-Liposome	Fluvastatin-15+Doxorubicin-3	Breast cancer-inhibited growth
Liposome	Simvastatin+Gefitinib	Lung cancer reversed resistance,Drug in metastasis
Liposome	Lovastatin+Doxorubicin	Liver cancer inhibited tumor growth
Herceptin coated liposome	Simvastatin+Doxorubicin	Prostate cancer - synergistic and angiogenesis effects
Liposome	Simvastatin+5-Fluorouracil	Colon cancer-reduced tumor growth
Hairpin liposome	Simvastatin+paclitaxel	Lung cancer-reverse epithelial-MSC, macrophages
Immuno-liposome	Simvastatin	Breast cancer HER2-apoptosis,ERK/AKT/tumor growth inhibition
Micelle	Simvastatin+Na-Alendronate	3-ve breast/Prostate/Lung adenocarcinoma-Inhibited tumor growth
Micelle nanoprobe	Simvastatin+ProtoporphyrinIX	Glioma-Cell cycle G1-S phase arrest, high apoptosis/reactive oxygen
Micelle	Atorvastatin	Glioblastoma/Glioma-inhibited cancer growth, high drug in tumor
Nanoemulsion-lipids	Atorvastatin	Intestinal cancer-inhibited tumor growth
Nanoemulsion-lipids	Doxorubicin+Pravastatin	Ehrlich ascites carcinoma-increased survival Breast cancer, Foreskin cancer-reduced cytotoxicity and side effects
Nanoemulsion	Simvastatin+Doxorubicin	Ehrlich ascites carcinoma-reduced cytotoxicity
Lipid nanoparticles	Atorvastatin	Breast cancer-increased bioavailability, growth inhibition
ChitosanEudragit-S100	Simvastatin	Colon cancer-reduced cytotoxicity, arrested G2/M phase
Chitosan-TGP PR-CNG-ER	Simvastatin	Breast cancer-High entrapment, controlled growth Liver cancer-better entrapment,drug loading, 2 day-sustained release
SVCSCs-NPs	Simvastatin, ASPGR	Hepatocellular carcinoma-inhibited proliferation, high cell uptake
PEG/lipids(Labrafil/Labrafac)	Simvastatin	Breast cancer-high cell viability in presence of Labrafil/Labrafac
PLGA-PEG-MAN	Simvastatin	HCC-Alleviate LSEC capillarisation,regressed stroma,NO signaling
PCL-PEG-PCL	Atorvastatin+Rosuvastatin	Breast cancer- inhibited growth, high cytotoxicity
PCL-PEG	Simvastatin	Breast cancer-sustained drug release, dose-specific growth inhibition
PCL-PEG	Simvastatin+5-Fluorouracil	Gastric cancer-induced apoptosis, autophagy, low metastasis
PLGA micron NP	Simvastatin	Breast cancer solid tumors-high AUC, $T_{1/2}$, C_{max} ,low K_{el}
PLGA	Simvastatin+Gemcitabine	Pancreatic/Breast cancers-high bioavailability/cytotoxicity,low IC_{50} value

With new understanding, statins inhibit the synthesis of farnesyl-pyrophosphate products and isoprenoid prenylation that form several apoptosis-stimulant proteins, proliferative proteins, immunomodulator proteins, inflammatory proteins, mito-redox and autophagy proteins as shown in

Figures 2 and 3. This way, statins act as anticancer “repurposed” drugs. Moreover, it remains inconclusive and federal un-approved mystery in clinical practice. For researchers and physicians, it is new excitement.

Fig. 2: Statin activated signaling pathways by Ras/Rho activation for oncogene upregulation towards arrested cell growth, differentiation, facilitated apoptosis and increased drug-resistance. Statins block isoprenoid synthesis and signaling cascades, to reduce cancer growth/differentiation and tumor progress [58].

Fig. 3: Synergistic additive action of statins in combination with anti-cancer drugs, statins suppress tumors by cell-cycle arrest, cell death, apoptosis, sensitization[13].

GLOBAL USE OF STATINS

Statin therapy was in use to treat heart diseases since the lovastatin first report on 1st September, 1987 in hypercholesterolemia treatment. Later statin was reported for its potential as

cancer adjuvant drug in the late 1990s years to reduce the mortality and cardiotoxicity with improvement in cancer survivors and patient outcomes [1]. Since then till present time, statins are continuously emerging as a possible

legalized and regulated ‘repurposed’ statin – chemoradiotherapy combination treatment option globally, however, their success or enhanced clinical or patient outcomes remain unestablished. Recently, novel statin – combined chemo-radio-immuno or targeted nanoformulations evolved as clinical solutions claimed by commercial pharmaceutical companies and hospitals across the world. Such rampant spread of statin reflections in cardiac and oncology clinics throughout UK, US, Europe, and Asia clearly reflects the public trust in statin benefits to incurable cancer and heart failure diseases.

The statin-chemoradiotherapy-immunotherapy ‘trimodal nanoformulations’ in combination therapy are designed based on rationale of different statins combined to different chemotherapeutic drugs and/or radiotherapy doses as engineered statin-chemoradiotherapy nanomedicines as shown in Table 1 and Figure 5. Current statin therapy federal regulations are used in different North American, European, and Asian countries. Presently, different FDA, CDC, EU and ICMR agencies contribute their inputs on ethical policies, regulatory oversight, and relevant laws on best practices of statin-based nanomedicine [2-4].

STATINS AS MULTI-PURPOSE DRUGS

Statins maintain human cardiomyocytes to restore the cardiovascular functions of heart and cardiovascular veins-arteries to repair the damaged human cardiovascular or myocardial tissues caused by trauma, genetic disease, or metabolic disease. In fact, statins inhibit HMG CoA-R and isoprenoid intermediate metabolites such as geranyl-geranyl-pyrophosphate and farnesyl pyrophosphate with prenylation to activate the apoptosis in low pH physiological conditions of tumor cells. In normal cell membrane synthesis requires

constantly the cholesterol at pH 7.45. Researchers will be excited to understand the fact how cancer cells stay in high oxidative stress or low pH < 7.0 and statin-blocked geranyl-geranyl-pyrophosphate and farnesyl pyrophosphate intermediates facilitate the prenylation and synthesis of: several caspases; BCL-2, VEGF, thrombospondin-2 apoptosis proteins; Ras, Rac, Rho, LDL-R proliferative proteins; immunomodulator CD40-80/CD86 proteins; ICAM, VCAM inflammatory proteins; mito-redox and MMP-9, NF- κ B, Rho-A autophagy proteins, in the tumors. These statin-induced different proteins trigger the activation of apoptosis with reduced autophagy, cell migration, and invasive effects to target the energy starved tumor cells [4]. Statins stimulate apoptosis with suppressed LDL-R, CDK, mTOR, p53, BCL-2, NF- κ B, AMPK pathways to reduce angiogenesis, inflammation, autophagy and metastasis. Now, statins in combination with chemotherapy and radiotherapy drugs safely caged in nanoassemblies are in market as ‘trimodal statin-chemo-radiotherapy’ nanoformulations.

Inside ‘trimodal’ nanoformulations, statins do lipid-lowering with statin-modulated signaling pathways such as Ras, Rho, and NF- κ B. Simultaneously, chemotherapy agents inside nanocage, inhibit proliferation and tumor multiplication to avoid metastasis. Also, high-energy internal-radiotherapy agents damage the DNA (tumor killing) to arrest tumor cell growth.

These molecular interactions in nanoformulation show inhibition of tumor proliferation, suppression of angiogenesis, induction of apoptosis, and modulation of immune responses in breast, prostate, lung, colorectal, pancreatic, hepatic, and pulmonary cancer preclinical models and clinical studies as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Clinical trial studies on statin loaded chemo-radiotherapy with enhanced patient outcome.

Clinical Study	Anticancer Drugs with Statins		Patient Outcome	Ref
Retrospective case-control study in BC(n=628)	Anthracycline	Atorvastatin	Incident HF and cancer-related low mortality in statin group	[19]
Retrospective study in BC,ALL,Lymphoma(n=51)	Anthracycline	Simvastatin, Atorvastatin	Declined LVEF by anthracyclines	[59]
Random-control trial(n=40)	Anthracycline	Atorvastatin	Maintained LVEF by anthracyclines	[60]
Double-blind radon-control trial on lymphoma(n=300)	Anthracycline chemotherapy	Atorvastatin	Reduced cardiac dysfunction by anthracyclines	[21]
Retrospective analysis in NSCLC patients(n=478)	Chemo-radiotherapy	Different Statins	Enhanced NSCL patient survival	[23]
Retrospective case-control study on HER2+ve Breast Cancer patients(n=525)	Trastuzumab therapy	Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin, Simvastatin, Pravastatin	Low risk of cardiotoxicity	[61]
Single center Study	ICI	Statins	ICI reduced atheroplaques	[62]
NCT06241352	Chemotherapy	Atorvastatin	Advanced Pancreatic cancer	NIH
NCT03971019	EBRT	Simvastatin	Breast cancer survival	NIH
NCT04601116(MASTER)	Chemodrug	Atorvastatin	ER+ve patient survival	NIH
NCT03024684(SHOT)	Curative Ther.	Atorvastatin	HCC recurrence/prevents	NIH
NCT04457089	Platinum	Simvastatin	Ovarian cancer low progression	NIH
NCT05696973(MOVES)	Exercise	Atorvastatin	Onco-exercise	NIH
NCT03560882(Pilot p53)	Chemodrug	Atorvastatin	P53 M/W malignancy	NIH
NCT03889795(Phase IB)	MetforminDigoxin	Simvastatin	Solid tumors	NIH
NCT06030622(Phase 2A-C3)	Metformin + Digoxin	Simvastatin	Recurrent/Refractory Pancreatic Cancer(C3)	NIH
NCT05550415	-	Simvastatin	Epithelial Mesenchymal Transition	NIH
NCT05977738(ReDiReCCT-P)	Calcium	Pitavastatin	Breast, Prostate cancers	NIH
NCT04767984	Calcium	Atorvastatin	Colon cancer+Ulcerative Colitis	NIH
NCT04491643	Megestrol Acetate	Rosuvastatin	Early endometrial carcinoma	NIH

PRESENT STATE-OF-ART ON STATINS: HOW MUCH WE KNOW?

From the reader’s point of view, new innovations are cited from the following evidenced recent reports.

- Statins perform in vitro and in vivo anticancer effects by mevalonate pathway modulation in human cancer cells [5].
- Statins serve as inhibitors of lung cancer, bone metastasis [6]
- Combination of Simvastatin and FAC Improves Response to Neoadjuvant Chemotherapy in Locally Advanced Breast Cancer [7]

- Statin doses were associated to radiation cardiotoxicity in non-small cell lung cancer NI-HEART study [8]
- Statins serve as ideal adjuvant therapeutic drugs with CCRT dose in nasopharyngeal cancer [9]
- Statin use during concurrent chemoradiotherapy enhanced the patient outcome in advanced nasopharyngeal cancer survivors [9]
- Statin improved the survival outcomes in esophageal squamous cell carcinoma [10]

- Statins show clinical potential of prostate cancer radiation therapy as adjuvant drugs [11].
- Statins are delivered with radiotherapy concurrent CCRT dose as combination therapy [12].
- Statins are used along with heart radiation dose to enhance the survival in locally advanced lung cancer [13]
- Repurposed statins, adiponectin and aspirins were suggested by ovarian Mendelian random analysis for ovarian cancer treatment. [14].
- Repurposed statin drugs reduce the disease burden in gynaec cancer [15]
- Statins in combination with other drugs are delivered in ovarian cancer treatment [16].
- Statins mitigate the cancer treatment induced CVD risks [17].
- Combination therapy of statin and chemotherapy drugs inhibits the proliferation and cytotoxicity of an aggressive natural killer cell leukemia [18]
- Statins serve as a repurposed drugs to fight against major cancers of esophagus, abdomen, liver, lung, breast, brain and heart [19].
- Repurposing statin drugs decrease the toxicity and improve the survival outcomes in head and neck cancer [20][21].
- Presently, there is paradigm shift on statins serve as anti-tumor agents as repurposed drugs [22].
- A protocol on statins in chemotherapy and radiotherapy enhanced targeting treatment of cancer Cells [23].
- Statin serve as a potential monotherapy, adjuvant chemotherapeutic agent for reducing anti-cancer chemodrug resistance [24].
- Clinical trials suggested the benefits of adding ezetimibe to statin therapy with latest evidences and clinical implications [25]
- The statins show effects on the chemoresistance either due to the antagonistic drug-drug interactions or due to the statin anti-cancer effects [26].
- Statins reduce the anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity by the effect of Rac and Rho proteins, and the heartbreakers [27]
- Statins may enhance the chemosensitivity of R-CHOP proteins in the diffuse large B-cell lymphoma cancer [28].
- Statins delivered with concurrent chemoradiotherapy vs radiotherapy alone in old-aged stage II nasopharyngeal carcinoma patients showed improved outcomes in propensity score-matched cohort study [29]
- Acute high-dose statin treatment improved the antibody accumulation in EGFR- and PSMA-expressing tumors [30]
- The hydrophilic statins with heart radiation dose improved the survival in locally advanced lung cancer [13].
- Statins reduce the toxicity on mitochondrial pathways to overcome the oxidative stress and free redical species as anticancer drugs [31].
- Statins delivery reduces the risk of cardiovascular events among cancer patients after radiotherapy to the thorax, head, and neck cancers [32].
- Simvastatins combined with antidiabetic drugs combination show synergistic effects as shown in Figure 3 in metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer [33].
- Induction chemotherapy is a new approach of statins with chemotherapy and subsequent radiotherapy and/or chemo-radiotherapy [34][35].

WHY STATINS ARE IN ACTIVE RESEARCH?

Statins are continuously in lime light as ‘repurposed drugs’ with growing preclinical evidences on different roles of statins for: 1. induced cancer cell apoptosis and autophagy; 2. inhibitors of chemotherapy and radiotherapy toxicities; 3. anti-stressors of decomposed-water ROS damage to normal cells; 4. suppressor of ET1 induced endothelial dysfunction, inflammation, fibrosis in normal cells; 5. restoring radiation therapy induced DNA damage, lipid peroxidation, protein nitrosylation, inhibition of IRS/PI3K/Akt pathways with enhanced MAPK signaling

pathway; 5. immunotherapy; 6. suppressor of CAR-T cell therapy, ICI therapies, induced cardiovascular complications of endothelial dysfunction, atherosclerosis plaque, myocarditis, arrhythmia, heart failure, thrombosis, vasculitis, thromboembolism and others; 7. antiproliferative therapy; 8. targeted therapy; 9. antioxidant therapy; 10. anti-angiogenesis therapy; 11. anti-inflammatory therapy; 12. antifibrotic therapy; 13. metastasis prevention therapy; and 14. antisense therapy as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: (On top) Trimodal therapy by statins combined with chemo-radiotherapy reduce anticancer drug resistance through induced cell cycle arrest, apoptosis, cytotoxicity and inhibition of signaling kinases in proliferation, growth, metastasis, angiogenesis, inflammation, and cell growth to kill tumors[13]. (at bottom) A general scheme of statin effects applied in different organ cancers [16]. Modified from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/cnr2.2078>.

Fig. 5: (On top) Different nanoassemblies. (On bottom) Preparation steps of carboxylated graphene oxide (CGO) and trimethyl chitosan (A, B) [16][82]. Preparation of siRNA loaded CGO-TMC-HA nanoparticles (C) [55][83].

For experimental research, normal or explanted tumor cells are harvested from explant-tumor propagated in animals after 3-4 months. Such tumor or cancer cell lines serve as biochemical-pharmacological therapeutic assays at different statin doses given in pre-determined normal and cultured cancer lines as proof-of-evidence.

From biologist's standpoint, the molecular basis of myocyte cells or explant tumor cells growing in 3D culture environments has explored several molecular controls of endothelial development and associated organs to understand the statin induced genetic control of cancer processes.

New clinical research is on the way of statin-modulation, repurposed roles in cardiovascular, heart diseases along with other benefits in untreatable diseases and life threats.

CLINICAL POTENTIALS OF STATINS TILL DATE

The first clinical trial took place in the United States for statin-based hypertension and heart prevention [36]. The first clinical trial on statin-based prostate cancer treatment was reported with reduced cardiotoxicity [37]. Later, in last three decades, statins have shown clinical potential as lipid metabolism modulators, inhibitors of cancer growth, adjuvant statin-chemo-radiotherapy nanoformulations to enhance the synergistic effects as metastasis suppressors as shown in Table 2.

UNMET CLINICAL CHALLENGES IN STATIN THERAPY

The hydrophilic or hydrophobic statins behave differently in tumors or cancers. So, optimized chemodrug or radiotherapy treatment or adjuvant immuno-therapy is needed as “trimodal therapy”. In support, six meta-analyses of randomized control trials (RCT) and two observational studies confirmed no association between statin use and overall incident cancer risk [38-40]. Single one meta-analysis showed reduced statin-mediated LDL-cholesterol with low cancer risk but inverse relationship of on-treatment LDL levels with cancer risk vs no statin treatment adjusted LDL effects on cancer risk [41].

Physicians have to be aware of limitations of clinical trial or observational studies such as short follow-up times, short statin use, no dose-duration response, selected groups of patients in RCTs, multiple statin types used in the meta-analyses. Most of the meta-analyses evaluated site-specific cancers showed null-findings [36-40]. On record, one meta-analysis of 17 RCTs, 10

cohort studies, and 15 case-control studies reported no benefit of statin use in reducing the lung, breast, or prostate cancer risk but clear protective effect in liver, stomach, lymphoma, melanoma and non-melanoma skin cancers [see Table 2]. Above reports reflect the unmet challenges of inconclusive statin use in cancer treatment. Major controversies still complicate the potentials of statin-based combination therapy [see Supplement 1].

GLOBAL REGULATORY NORMS FOR STATIN RESEARCH

What are governmental stands on statins in human heart and cancer treatment? Since last over 40 years, statins were proven as cholesterol lowering drugs with new concerns of induced carcinogenicity in breast, colorectal, lung, prostate, and reproductive organs [39]. In the United States of America, lovastatin, pravastatin, simvastatin, fluvastatin, atorvastatin, and rosuvastatin are in market. Pravastatin and simvastatin showed adverse effects but their tumor-recurrence reducing effect was remarkable [55]. Out of 27 countries in the European Union (EU), only three countries prohibit high-dose statins (Poland, Latvia, and Slovakia) and the rest have no specific legislation. The EU legislation on cancer therapy (no statin word) is based on three directives: (1) directive 2003/63/EC on therapy products; (2) directive 2001/20/EC on clinical trial outcome; (3) directive 2004/23/EC on quality, safety for cancer.

REGULATIONS AND POLICY ON STATINS IN HUMAN RESEARCH AND CLINICAL USE?

In US, EU member States and Asia, both US and EU have own clear ethical and legal framework on statin batch consistency, statin stability, safety, efficacy, and quality of statin- combination protocols through pre-clinical, clinical, and marketing authorization. In US, in year 2013, American College of Cardiology/ American Heart Association reported

guideline-based statin eligibility criteria to reduce CVD-composite risk with cancer risk as primary outcome and identify high mortalities from cancer and non-cardiovascular disease [42][43][44]. Existing guidelines outline statin dosage in appropriate patient populations [45]. Clinical trials demonstrate the benefits of guidelines, case-by-case treatment decisions, with no legislation or policy [46].

ETHICAL GUIDELINES FOR STATIN RESEARCH IN INDIA ON HUMAN SUBJECTS

Statin research and therapy (by Indian Council of Medical Research, ICMR 2005) defines the use of clinical grade statins for clinical trials on dyslipidemia and cardiovascular health approved by institution committee at multinational companies or from abroad. In the year 2024, Corpseed Info proposed amendment rules aligned with global standards for an attractive destination for pharmaceutical research globally.[47]. ICMR, Indian pharmacopeia laid down “Guidelines for Statin Research and Therapy” in the year 2018 on mechanism of diabetes type II. Central Drug Standards Control Organization (CDSCO) defined guidelines on new statin products. As a result, national committee proposed as “national Health Authority” by ICMR to approve the statin therapeutic products of human use, and combination nano-formulations in market since year 2019.[48].

INTERNATIONAL UNANIMOUS OPINION

No international guidelines recommend statins for cancer prevention or treatment [49]. In this direction, statin combination with other cancer therapies is exciting research. Previous 2018 AHA/ACC/MS and 2022 USPSTF guidelines for statin therapy advocated the statin-reduced ASCVD risk in young adults and patients with diabetes mellitus [50]. American

Heart Association (AHA) and European Society of Cardiology (ESC) focus on statins to reduce cardiovascular disease risk in hypercholesterolemia patients with risk of heart attack or stroke [51]. Observational studies in different continents have suggested an inconclusive potential link between statin and reduced risk of certain colorectal, prostate, breast and pancreatic cancers [52].

HOW MUCH HAVE THE US AND EU SPENT ON STATIN RESEARCH?

In the years 2007–2017, the US channeled in REPRIEVE trial through National Institutes of Health (NIH), National heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (NHLBI), National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) and NIH funds RO1 research grants and clinical trial grants. NIH contracts systematic reviews conducted for the US Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF). NIH supports agreements and NIH-external investigator collaborations. The Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) funds USPSTF to provide recommendations on the use of statins for primary prevention of cardiovascular disease. Present research addresses long-term effects, role in specific populations and potential of personalized treatment approaches. [53]. EU has funded 27 collaborative health research projects involving Horizon Europe and Innovative Health Initiative. EU has funded “IndivStat” to focus on individual statin therapy for hypercholesterolemia.

STATIN-IN-COMBINATION

THERAPY: A SUCCESS OR A MYTH

The ‘trimodal therapy’ as statin-chemo-radiotherapy with or without immunotherapy enhances the patient outcome and slows down the tumor reoccurrence. Statins do cardiovascular prevention as cholesterol-lowering process. The inconclusive half-way RCTs, observational studies suggested the statins

to increase the chemo-radiotherapy sensitization with enhanced patient outcomes while clinical trials do not fully support the anticancer statin potentials but indicate the benefits. Statins inhibit the mevalonate–isoprenoid farnesyl-PP product after protein prenylation that triggers the multifaceted apoptosis-autophagy-mito ox-angiogenesis-immune control-inflammation processes towards cancer growth. Statins inhibit them all that appears as “myth” without support of clinical trials, government policy, federal guidelines and half-way observational studies [54][55].

STATIN TREATMENT IN CANCER AND NANOFORMULATION PRODUCTS

Clinical development for first-in-man statin nanoformulation (EMA/CHMP/SWP/28367/07) design

demonstrated new investigational product and over fifty others [56].

WHAT IS ALTERNATIVE STATIN IN-COMBINATION NANOFORMULATIONS?

Nanoformulations are mainly nanocarriers as cages loaded with statins, chemodrugs and radiotherapy sensitizer agents. Nanoformulations act as robust, pH dependent controlled release polymer nanomaterials such as liposomes, emulsions, micelles, graphenes, polyethylene glycol (PEG), PGLA, chitosan and others [57]. In the tumor microenvironment at low pH, these nanocages release the statins with chemo and radiotherapy agents as per need in sequence to inhibit the tumor cell functions and minimize tumor growth as illustrated with representative preclinical evidence in Table 3.

Table 3: A physician's guide on different statin doses given in combination with chemotherapy drugs showing evidence of benefits in different organ cancers [58]. Reproduced from the original source by Ahmadi Y et al. 2018[58].

Statin	Dose/Concentration	Anti-tumor agent	Cancer cell/case	Effects of co-therapy
Atorva.	0.04% in diet ¹ ; 0.75-9 μM ² ; 8-40 μM ³ 9-18 μM ⁴ ; 9 μM ⁵	Nobiletin (a citrus polymethoxyflavone)	HT29 human colorectal cancer cells and RAW 264.7 macrophages and rat colon cancer model	Suppression of colon carcinogenesis ¹ ; enhanced the growth inhibitory effects ² , anti-inflammatory effects ³ , cytostatic effects ⁴ and apoptosis ⁵ .
Fluva.	0.1-20 μM	Gemcitabine	Pancreatic cancer cell line (MIAPaCa-2)	Synergistically enhanced the anti-neoplastic effects of gemcitabine.
Lova.	50 μM	Enzastaurin	Hepatocellular carcinoma	Significantly increased the anti-neoplastic effect of enzastaurin both in vivo and in vitro
Prava.	25 mg/kg*	5-Fluorouracil (5-FU)	Mouse HCC model ¹	Significantly increased the cytotoxic effects of 5-FU and survival of patients
Atorva.	daily dose of 40 mg 9 μM ² and 0.72 μM	Tocotrienols (T3s)	Advanced HCC patients HT29 ² and HCT116 colon cancer cells	Significantly increased the inhibitory effects of Tocotrienols on the cancer cell growth/survival and cell cycle.
Lova.	0, 5, 10, and 30 μM	Cisplatin, 5-FU	Colon cancer cells SW480, HCT116; LoVo, and HT29	Synergistically enhanced the cisplatin/5-FU-induced apoptosis
Atorva.	10 μM (cells) 5 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (xenograft animal)	Celecoxib	Prostate adenocarcinoma cell line (LNCaP); mice with Xenograft LNCaP human tumor	Increase in the inhibitory effect of celecoxib on the cell growth and cancer progression. Decrease in the progression of the androgen-dependent LNCaP prostate tumors in the castrated mice.
Lova.	100 mg/day	Cisplatin	MB16 melanoma-bearing B6D/F1 mice	Increase in the anti-tumor effects of cisplatin
Lova. Prava.	10 μM (lova.) 200 μM (prava.)	Doxorubicin	KG1a drug-naïve, primitive leukemia cells	Lowastatin and pravastatin decreased the P-gp protein expression by 26% and 16% respectively; Sensitized these cells to daunorubicin.
Lova.	10 μM	Paclitaxel	Human leukemia cell lines, K562 and HL-60	Increase in the paclitaxel-induced cell cycle arrest at G2/M and the paclitaxel-induced apoptosis without increasing cellular P-glycoprotein levels
Simva.	40 mg/day	Gefitinib	Gefitinib-resistant NSCLC (non-small cell lung cancer) patients	Increase in the cytotoxic effects of gefitinib.
Lova.	15 mg/kg	Doxorubicin	Several murine tumor cell lines (v-Ha-ras-transformed NIH-3T3 sarcoma cells, Colon-26 cells, and Lewis lung carcinoma cells)	Increased in the cytostatic/cytotoxic effect of doxorubicin. Significant reduction in the circulatory level of the troponin T in the doxorubicin-treated mice, showing that lovastatin reduces the adverse effects of doxorubicin on the heart
Atorva.	20 mg/kg	MTX	Solid Ehrlich tumor in mice	More efficient effect than monotherapy of methotrexate or atorvastatin alone
Atorva. Prava.	4, 5 μM	Topoisomerase-I inhibitor SN38	HepG2 cell	Reduction in the hypoxic resistance of HCC to SN38, through the inhibitory effects on hypoxic-activated YAP (Yes-Associated Protein)
Simva.	10 μM	Capecitabine	Xenograft mouse model of human gastric cancer	Increase in the tumor growth inhibitory effects of capecitabine via downregulation of NF- κB activation.
Simva.	5-35 μM	Doxorubicin	BFTC-905-DONO- II bladder cancer cell line	Restored sensitivity of BFTC-905-DONO- II to doxorubicin comparable to that of the parental cell line.
Simva.	5-20 μM	BH3 (BCL2 homology domain-3) mimetics venetoclax and navitoclax	Primary leukemia (AML) and lymphoma (DLBCL) cells	Increase in the pro-apoptotic activity of B cell lymphoma-2 (BCL2) inhibitor venetoclax (ABT-199) in primary leukemia and lymphoma cells but not in normal human peripheral blood mononuclear cells.

The approach of trimodal statin-chemoradio-immunotherapy caged in nano-assemblies enhanced the patient outcomes[58]. These nanoformulations travel safely in vicinity of aggressive tumor with least cytotoxicity to normal cells around. There are various types of ‘tissue-specific statin-chemotherapy’ combinations useful in specific anticancer applications. Different hydrophilic and hydrophobic statins combine to chemodrugs such as cisplatin, anthracyclins, trastuzumab, ezetimibe.

ETHICAL CONCERNS ON STATIN THERAPY

Statin therapy have own benefits and risks. Specific regulations and ethics guidelines were introduced in the European Union (EU) in H2020 [59] and Federal Drug Agency [FDA] to manage the risks. Security and control of statin medicines is tightly controlled by the FDA in US and CDC in EU [60].

HOW STATINS IN CANCER AND HEART DISEASE TREATMENT CLINICS ARE REGULATED IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES?

In a very short span of two decades, over 600 reports supported the claim of statin-reduced onco-cardiotoxicity (SOC) events in cancer survivors living with CVD and CHD. European (EU), Federal Drug Agency (FDA), Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), Asian nations (ASEAN) agencies advocated the statin role in reducing cardiovascular risks [61].

CONCLUSION

Statins might offer benefits and pleiotropic effects as antithrombotic, anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiproliferative and anti-metastatic nanocaged nanomedicine for cancer management with least cardiac health risk. Statin-associated muscle symptoms (SAMS) are myopathy, pain, stiffness, cramps, weakness, exertion due to statin intolerance. The statin drug-

resistance is due to SREBP-2, MDR-1, TGF- β 1 proteins and MRP2/ABCC2, CETP, HMG-CoAR, TNF- α , BCRP/ABCG2, P-gp/ABCB1, MRP1/ABCC1, ApoE, NPC-1L1, RHOA, CYP7A1, LDLR, OATP gene polymorphisms. Statins may be anti-proliferative tumor preventive drugs. Phase I and II clinical trials on simvastatin and pravastatin with cyclosporine A, mitoxantrone and etoposide induced toxicity. In future, more data, more clinical trials and their validation will decide the fate of statins in cancer treatment at low cytotoxicity and low cardiotoxicity.

SUPPLEMENT 1: CONTROVERSIES

1. Most of the clinical trials show conflicting results on statins induce anticancer drug effects in cancer treatment with widely varying mechanisms of action across different cancer types and statin subtypes. Few studies only suggest that statins reduce cancer risk and mortality in breast, prostate and colorectal cancers while statins show no significant benefits or even no potential harm.
2. Limited controversial observational studies indicate that statins are associated with lower risk of developing some cancers such as breast, colorectal, prostate cancer (low mortality), and improved cancer survival rates.
3. Statins inhibit the rapid isoprenylation of isoprenes and geranylgeranyl pyrophosphate conversion to radical formation or caspase enzyme control on apoptosis, autophagy, angiogenesis and cell cycle regulation / modulation. However, statins' role and mechanism in apoptosis, autophagy, cell cycle regulation is not confirmed.
4. The controversial role of statins in combination treatment with chemotherapy and immunotherapy is poorly claimed to enhance the effectiveness.
5. Many prospective clinical trials have not shown significant statin benefits in

cancer treatment but highlighted the need of clarification on statin role in advanced cancer.

6. Hydrophilic and hydrophobic statins behave differently on different heterogeneous cancer types. 7. Some studies indicated that statins increase the risk of prostate cancer and melanoma with adverse effects on specific cancer types.

8. Many cofounding factors of life style choice, medications in some observational studies showed their interference with statins influence on cancer risk and mortality.

9. No authentic biomarkers are available to predict the statin therapy patient response, hindering personalized cancer therapy strategy.

10. Future research on statin long-term cohort studies, mechanistic studies, combination therapy and personalized medicine may certainly explore the concrete statin benefits in cancer treatment.

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